

angiopoietin like 7 or cornea-derived transcript 6 (ANGPTL7 / CDT6) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : Angiopoietins are vascular growth factors that play a role in embryonic and postnatal angiogenesis. The Angiopoietin-like proteins are proteins structurally like the angiopoietins but which do not bind to the angiopoietin receptors. ANGPTL7 is one of the eight Angiopoietin-like proteins. It is implicated in intraocular pressure, glaucoma, human cancers, hair follicles, obesity, Angiotensin II (AngII) induced hypertension, vascular thickening, atherosclerosis, acute heart failure, insulin resistance, type 2 diabetes mellitus, cord blood of preterm infants, obstructive sleep apnea, Gestational diabetes mellitus and myocardial hypertrophy, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2nd order combinations of ANGPTL7, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible

*ML dicoveries of ANGPTL7 synergy in Meningiomas

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hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: ANGPTL7, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective membranes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplas-

tic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagioccephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. angipoietin like 7 (ANGPTL7)

Peek et al. [13] isolated tissue-specific gene products that contribute to corneal integrity, for which a cDNA library was constructed and differentially hybridized. In addition to known cornea-specific gene products, they isolated a transcript coding for a protein homologous to the angipoietins. On sequencing the full cDNA, the identified

open reading frame was named cornea-derived transcript 6 (CDT6). They observed that similar to the angiopoietins, CDT6 contains a hydrophobic NH₂-terminal sequence, a coiled-coil domain, and a COOH-terminal fibrinogenlike domain. They detected the expression of CDT6 only in the cornea and not in several other adult human tissues. Further, within the cornea, expression of CDT6 is confined to the stromal layer. They concluded that the human cornea showed high-level expressions of a gene product homologous to the (anti)angiogenic factors, the angiopoietins and this homology, together with stromal-specific expression, showed that this factor might contribute to the avascularity of the human cornea.

Peek et al. [14] reported the structural and functional characterization of CDT6, where they demonstrated that CDT6 was a secreted protein that folds into disulfide-linked homotetramers by coiled-coil interactions. To test the hypothesis that CDT6 expressed at high levels in the avascular corneal stromal layer, acted as a negative regulator of angiogenesis and to assay the effect of the protein on a growing tissue with high vascular density, they expressed CDT6 in a mouse xenograft model. They observed that CDT6 expression led to a reduction in tumor growth and aberrant blood vessel formation by inducing massive fibrosis. Also, they found that expression of CDT6 resulted in the deposition of extracellular matrix components typical for the mature corneal stromal layer. These observations suggested a role as morphogen for CDT6 in inducing a corneal phenotype in vivo.

1.3. Roles of ANGPTL7 in different disease

The trabecular meshwork tissue controls the drainage of the aqueous humor of the eye and a dysfunctional trabecular meshwork leads to an altered fluid resistance, which results in increased **intraocular pressure** (IOP). IOP is the major risk factor of **glaucoma**, the second-leading cause of blindness in the developed world. Comes et al. [15] identified angiopoietin-like7 (ANGPTL7) while searching for genes altered by glaucomatous insults. They found that overexpression of ANGPTL7 in primary human trabecular meshwork cells altered the expression of fibronectin, collagens type I, IV & V, myocilin, versican, and MMP1. Further, they observed that ANGPTL7 also interfered with the fibrillar assembly of fibronectin. They found that silencing ANGPTL7 during the glucocorticoid insult significantly affected the expression of other steroid-responsive proteins. These results indicate that ANGPTL7 modulates the trabecular meshwork's ECM and its properties strengthen ANGPTL7's candidacy for the regulation of IOP and glaucoma.

Some ANGPTL proteins possess pleiotropic activities, being involved in cancer lipid, glucose energy metabolisms, and angiogenesis. Parri et al. [16] provided experimental evidences that ANGPTL7 was over-expressed in different **human cancers**. They found that ANGPTL7 was marginally expressed under standard growth condition while it is specifically up-regulated by hypoxia. ANGPTL7 was also secreted and partially associated with the exosomal fraction, suggesting that it could be found in the systemic circulation of oncologic patients and act in an endocrine way. Moreover, they found that ANGPTL7 exerted a pro-angiogenic effect on human differentiated endothelial cells by stimulating their proliferation, motility, invasiveness, and capability to form capillary-like networks while it did not stimulate progenitor endothelial cells.

Finally, they showed that ANGPTL7 promoted vascularization in vivo in the mouse Matrigel sponge assay, thereby accrediting this molecule as a pro-angiogenic factor.

Adaptation to the space environment can sometimes pose physiological problems to International Space Station (ISS) astronauts after their return to earth. Terada et al. [17] examined the feasibility of using **hair follicles**, a readily obtained sample, to assess gene expression changes in response to spaceflight adaptation. Analysing gene expression changes in hair follicles of 10 astronauts, they found that spaceflight altered human hair follicle gene expression. In some astronauts, genes related to hair growth such as FGF18, ANGPTL7 and COMP were upregulated during flight, suggesting that spaceflight inhibits cell proliferation in hair follicles.

Abu-Farha et al. [18] showed that ANGPTL7 level was increased in the plasma of obese subjects (1249.05 ± 130.39 pg/mL) as compared to non-obese (930.34 ± 87.27 pg/mL). Further, ANGPTL7 gene and protein expression levels in adipose tissue were found to be over 2-fold increase. Physical exercise reduced circulating level of ANGPTL7 in the obese subjects to 740.98 ± 127.18 pg/mL and ANGPTL7 expression in adipose tissue was also reduced after exercise. Finally, they observed that the circulating level of ANGPTL7 showed significant association with TG level in the obese subjects ($R^2 = 0.183$, $p\text{-Value} = 0.03$). In a first, their data showed that **obesity** increased the level of ANGPTL7 in both plasma and adipose tissue. Also, physical exercise reduced the level of ANGPTL7, thus highlighting the potential for targeting this protein as a therapeutic target for regulating dyslipidemia.

Angiotensin II (AngII) induces hypertension and pathophysiological **vascular thickening** and **atherosclerosis**. Zhao et al. [19] aimed to validate the effects of ANGPTL7 in AngII-induced hypertension and found high expression of ANGPTL7 in patients with hypertension. AngII promoted cell viability and the expression level of ANGPTL7 in vascular smooth muscle cells (VSMC) and they observed that downregulation of ANGPTL7 inhibited AngII-induced cell proliferation and cell inflammation. Moreover, ANGPTL7 expression decreased also promoted cell apoptosis.

Zhang et al. [20] evaluated the association between ANGPTL7 and short-term mortality due to **acute heart failure** (AHF). For this, patients with AHF were studied and serum levels of ANGPTL7 were measured by an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. Associations between 30- and 90-day mortality and tertiles of ANGPTL7 were assessed by multivariate logistic regression models. They concluded that serum level of ANGPTL7 was independently associated with short-term mortality among patients with AHF.

Tumor necrosis factor- α promotes monocyte adhesion to endothelium and accumulation of endothelium will lead to atherosclerosis. Li et al. [21] explored ANGPTL7 as a potential target in the process of **atherosclerosis**, and its role in the adhesion and oxidative stress induced by TNF- α in human umbilical vein epithelial cells (HUVEC). The initiation of atherosclerosis is endothelial injury. They observed that ANGPTL7 was dramatically increased in TNF- α -induced HUVEC compared to the control cells while its inhibition significantly reversed TNF- α -induced cell adhesion in HUVEC. They concluded that ANGPTL7 might participate in the development of endothelial injury and further atherosclerosis.

Xu et al. [22] demonstrated that ANGPTL7 promoted **insulin resistance** and **type 2 diabetes mellitus** (T2DM), as they found that the circulating ANGPTL7 levels in

T2DM patient and mouse models were significantly elevated. Furthermore, in vivo overexpression of ANGPTL7 in experimental healthy mice also caused insulin resistance-like characteristics. Also, it was observed that over-expressed ANGPTL7 inhibited the phosphorylation of AKT and promoted the phosphorylation of ERK1/2, which was known to be associated with insulin resistance. They provide strong evidence that ANGPTL7 promoted insulin resistance and T2DM by multiple mechanisms.

Xia et al. [23] investigated the concentration of ANGPTL7 in **cord blood of preterm infants**, for which singleton infants (182 in number) born in November 2017 to June 2019 in the study hospital were enrolled in the study. They found ANGPTL7 levels in preterm infants were significantly higher than that in full-term babies. They concluded that the levels are independently influenced by gestational ages and attenuated significantly after birth. The underlying mechanism needs to be further studied.

Leentjens et al. [24] explored the link between ANGPTL7 and **obstructive sleep apnea (OSA)** in patients with different OSA severity. Furthermore, they examined the effect of treating OSA with bariatric surgery on ANGPTL7 level. They observed higher levels of circulating ANGPTL7 in people with moderate-to-severe OSA (1440 ± 1310 pg/ml) compared to the none or mild OSA group (734 ± 904 pg/ml, $p = 0.01$). The increase in ANGPTL7 correlated significantly and positively with the apnea-hypopnea index (AHI, $r = .226$, $p = .037$), and AHI-supine ($r = .266$, $p = .019$) in participants with moderate-to-severe OSA. Further, they found that bariatric surgery reduced the levels of both ANGPTL7 and AHI significantly. In conclusion, they reported significantly increased levels of ANGPTL7 both in the circulation and in adipose tissue of patients with OSA, which concurred with increased inflammation and OSA severity. Levels of ANGPTL7 decreased significantly as OSA showed a significant improvement post-surgery supporting a potential role for ANGPTL7 in either OSA progression or a role in an OSA-related mechanism.

Gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) can negatively impact newborn cardiac health, particularly causing **myocardial hypertrophy**. Jian et al. [25] examined the relationship between umbilical cord blood levels of ANGPTL7 in term neonates (46 in number) born to mothers with GDM and myocardial development. They observed that the incidence of myocardial hypertrophy in the GDM group was 19.6%, significantly higher than 0% in the control group, and increased to 27.3% in neonates of mothers with GDM and poor glycaemic control. Further, ANGPTL7 levels in the GDM group were significantly elevated compared to the control group (1.87 vs. 1.11 ng/mL). Also, these levels were positively correlated with IVS thickness. In the poorly-controlled GDM subgroup (GDM-A), neonates had significantly higher ANGPTL7 levels and IVS/LVPW ratio (1.19 vs. 1.03), indicating more severe myocardial abnormalities. They concluded that ANGPTL7 might contribute to myocardial hypertrophy in GDM neonates by promoting insulin resistance.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [26] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2^{nd} order gene combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [27] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [27].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on

gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [28]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of formating the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [29], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [26] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [26]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [30], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")` • use `source("manuscript-2-2.R")` • use `source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R")`.

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings

provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. ANGPTL7 related synergies

Note - ANGPTL7 was found to be upregulated in Type A. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 307 2^{nd} order combinations of ANGPTL7 were recorded.

3.1.1. ANGPTL7 - individual genes

The following genes in combination with ANGPTL7 showed high rankings - anosmin 1 (ANOS1), malic enzyme 1 (ME1), molybdenum cofactor sulfurase (MOCOS), spermine oxidase (SMOX), EBF family member 4 (EBF4), ezrin (EZR), BMP and activin membrane bound inhibitor (BAMBI), Josephin domain containing 1 (JOSD1), papilin, proteoglycan like sulfated glycoprotein (PAPLN), eukaryotic translation elongation factor 1 alpha 2 (EEF1A2), WAP four-disulfide core domain 2 (WFDC2), glutamate ionotropic receptor kainate type subunit 5 (GRIK5), nicotinamide phosphoribosyltransferase (NAMPT), Rap guanine nucleotide exchange factor like 1 (RAPGEFL1), sodium channel epithelial 1 subunit alpha (SCNN1A), mannosidase alpha class 1A member 1 (MAN1A1), FA complementation group E (FANCE), phosphatase and actin regulator 1 (PHACTR1), acyl-CoA dehydrogenase long chain (ACADL), SSX family member 2 interacting protein (SSX2IP), endothelin converting enzyme 1 (ECE1), solute carrier family 16 member 7 (SLC16A7), ATP binding cassette subfamily C member 4 (PEL blood group) (ABCC4), tubulin alpha 4a (TUBA4A), LIF interleukin 6 family cytokine (LIF), filamin C (FLNC), fibroblast growth factor 13 (FGF13), low density lipoprotein receptor (LDLR), argininosuccinate synthase 1 (ASS1), LARGE xylosyl- and glucuronyltransferase 1 (LARGE1), unc-79 subunit of NALCN channel complex (UNC79), tetratricopeptide repeat domain 9 (TTC9), proline rich and Gla domain 4 (PRRG4), GIPC PDZ domain containing family member 2 (GIPC2), RasGEF domain family member 1B (RASGEF1B), cyclin dependent kinase like 2 (CDKL2), kinesin family member 21A (KIF21A), ring finger protein 157 (RNF157), solute carrier family 47 member 1 (SLC47A1), solute carrier family 44 member 3 (SLC44A3), serine protease 35 (PRSS35), astrotactin 2 (ASTN2), coiled-coil domain containing 81 (CCDC81), inter-alpha-trypsin inhibitor heavy chain 2 (ITIH2), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit alpha2delta 1 (CACNA2D1), neural cell adhesion molecule 2 (NCAM2), solute carrier family 26 member 2 (SLC26A2), chloride intracellular channel 2 (CLIC2), glutamate receptor interacting protein 1 (GRIP1), SH3 domain containing ring finger 2 (SH3RF2), angiotensin I converting enzyme (ACE), spondin 2 (SPON2), cholinergic receptor nicotinic beta 2 subunit (CHRN2), cytochrome P450 family 3 subfamily A member 4 (CYP3A4), Rho guanine nucleotide exchange factor 3 (ARHGAP3), solute carrier family 9 member B2 (SLC9B2), adeny-

late cyclase 1 (ADCY1), transient receptor potential cation channel subfamily V member 6 (TRPV6), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL), protein phosphatase 1 regulatory subunit 36 (PPP1R36), calcium voltage-gated channel auxiliary subunit beta 2 (CACNB2), serine peptidase inhibitor, Kunitz type 1 (SPINT1), sodium voltage-gated channel beta subunit 3 (SCN3B), alanyl aminopeptidase, membrane (ANPEP), small G protein signaling modulator 1 (SGSM1), HRAS-like suppressor family, member 5 (HRASLS5), phytanoyl-CoA 2-hydroxylase interacting protein like (PHYHIPL), neuronal vesicle trafficking associated 1 (NSG1), anoctamin 5 (ANO5), cilia and flagella associated protein 46 (CFAP46), interferon stimulated exonuclease gene 20 (ISG20), membrane bound glycerophospholipid O-acyltransferase 1 (MBOAT1), serine palmitoyltransferase long chain base subunit 3 (SPTLC3), cold shock domain containing C2 (CSDC2), regulator of calcineurin 2 (RCAN2), radial spoke head component 9 (RSPH9), carboxylesterase 4A (CES4A), primary cilia formation (PIFO), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 2A1 (SLCO2A1), solute carrier family 35 member G1 (SLC35G1), family with sequence similarity 91 member A1 (FAM91A1), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily A member 2 (KCNA2), LRRN4 C-terminal like (LRRN4CL), G protein-coupled receptor 4 (GPR4), reprimin, TP53 dependent G2 arrest mediator homolog (RPRM), transmembrane protein 125 (TMEM125), WSC domain containing 1 (WSCD1), synemin (SYNM), calpain 12 (CAPN12), receptor interacting serine/threonine kinase 4 (RIPK4), coiled-coil serine rich protein 1 (CCSER1), short chain dehydrogenase/reductase family 42E, member 1 (SDR42E1), MAF bZIP transcription factor F (MAFF), RNA binding motif protein 11 (RBM11), potassium voltage-gated channel interacting protein 4 (KC-NIP4), NF2, moesin-ezrin-radixin like (MERLIN) tumor suppressor (NF2), BCR activator of RhoGEF and GTPase (BCR), natural killer cell cytotoxicity receptor 3 ligand 1 (NCR3LG1), family with sequence similarity 78 member B (FAM78B), FAT atypical cadherin 4 (FAT4), solute carrier family 6 member 9 (SLC6A9), ectonucleotide pyrophosphatase/phosphodiesterase 1 (ENPP1), AFDN divergent transcript (AFDN-DT), SH3 domain binding glutamate rich protein like 2 (SH3BGRL2), ankyrin repeat domain 35 (ANKRD35), sterol regulatory element binding transcription factor 2 (SREBF2), collagen type XV alpha 1 chain (COL15A1) and chromosome 9 open reading frame 129 (C9orf129).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of ANGPTL7 with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t ANGPTL7 with ANGPTL7 → ANOS1 / ME1 / MOCOS / SMOX / EBF4 / EZR / BAMBI / JOSD1 / PAPLN / EEF1A2 / WFDC2 / GRIK5 / NAMPT / RAPGEFL1 / SCNN1A / MAN1A1 / FANCE / PHACTR1 / ACADL / SSX2IP / ECE1 / SLC16A7 / ABCC4 / TUBA4A / LIF / FLNC / FGF13 / LDLR / ASS1 / LARGE1 / UNC99 / TTC9 / PRRG4 / GIPC2 / RASGEF1B / CDKL2 / KIF21A / RNF157 / SLC47A1 / SLC44A3 / PRSS35 / ASTN2 / CCDC81 / ITIH2 / CACNA2D1 / NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 / SH3RF2 / ACE / SPON2 / CHRNB2 / CYP3A4 / ARHGEF3 / SLC9B2 / ADCY1 / TRPV6 / PHYHIPL /

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS ANGPTL7									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T ANGPTL7									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ANOS1 - ANGPTL7	165	12	201	221	ME1 - ANGPTL7	209	53	221	167
MOCOS - ANGPTL7	284	80	243	161	SMOX - ANGPTL7	262	40	156	241
EBF4 - ANGPTL7	162	68	250	170	EZR - ANGPTL7	214	283	138	234
BAMBI - ANGPTL7	206	165	109	180	JOSD1 - ANGPTL7	199	11	223	165
PAPLN - ANGPTL7	204	33	169	287	EEF1A2 - ANGPTL7	255	183	78	253
WFDC2 - ANGPTL7	177	228	163	207	GRIK5 - ANGPTL7	146	169	179	201
NAMPT - ANGPTL7	269	188	230	111	RAPGEFL1 - ANGPTL7	267	191	217	304
SCNN1A - ANGPTL7	219	144	225	191	MAN1A1 - ANGPTL7	195	97	197	174
FANCE - ANGPTL7	71	163	158	281	PHACTR1 - ANGPTL7	232	73	171	188
ACADL - ANGPTL7	183	158	29	259	SSX2IP - ANGPTL7	254	8	188	192
ECE1 - ANGPTL7	253	143	187	271	SLC16A7 - ANGPTL7	226	174	196	193
ABCC4 - ANGPTL7	105	221	206	235	TUBA4A - ANGPTL7	259	274	88	204
LIF - ANGPTL7	150	37	192	184	FLNC - ANGPTL7	192	87	214	209
FGF13 - ANGPTL7	202	141	151	154	LDLR - ANGPTL7	264	1	153	225
ASS1 - ANGPTL7	191	65	150	176	LARGE1 - ANGPTL7	275	102	227	171
UNC79 - ANGPTL7	239	159	216	217	TTC9 - ANGPTL7	139	216	259	215
PRRG4 - ANGPTL7	294	10	178	157	GIPC2 - ANGPTL7	176	54	215	185
RASGEF1B - ANGPTL7	234	265	235	121	CDKL2 - ANGPTL7	272	178	49	250
KIF21A - ANGPTL7	203	267	255	143	RNF157 - ANGPTL7	203	267	255	143
SLC47A1 - ANGPTL7	279	49	222	179	SLC44A3 - ANGPTL7	295	202	185	242
PRSS35 - ANGPTL7	173	66	254	164	ASTN2 - ANGPTL7	175	212	137	262
CCDC81 - ANGPTL7	158	27	154	305	ITIH2 - ANGPTL7	119	168	159	181
CACNA2D1 - ANGPTL7	278	166	186	117	NCAM2 - ANGPTL7	261	103	182	256
SLC26A2 - ANGPTL7	256	199	160	227	CLIC2 - ANGPTL7	227	235	212	173
GRIP1 - ANGPTL7	36	245	203	249	SH3RF2 - ANGPTL7	168	3	256	224
ACE - ANGPTL7	297	209	191	148	SPON2 - ANGPTL7	273	193	136	291
CHRN2 - ANGPTL7	230	106	210	278	CYP3A4 - ANGPTL7	21	153	165	265

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between ANGPTL7 VS Individual members.

PPP1R36 / CACNB2 / SPINT1 / SCN3B / ANPEP / SGSM1 / PLAAT5 / PHYHIPL / NSG1 / ANO5 / CFAP46 / ISG20 / MBOAT1 / SPTLC3 / CSDC2 / RCAN2 / RSPH9 / CES4A / PIFO / SLCO2A1 / SLC35G1 / FAM91A1 / KCNA2 / LRRN4CL / GPR4 / RPRM / TMEM125 / WSCD1 / SYNM / CAPN12 / RIPK4 / CCSER1 / SDR42E1 / MAFF / RBM11 / KCNIP4 / NF2 / BCR / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / FAT4 / SLC6A9 / ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 / ANKRD35 / SREBF2 / COL15A1 / C9orf129.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic ANGPTL7 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of ANGPTL7-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS ANGPTL7									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T ANGPTL7									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
ARHGEF3 - ANGPTL7	197	234	228	190	SLC9B2 - ANGPTL7	229	17	184	166
ADCY1 - ANGPTL7	200	132	173	159	TRPV6 - ANGPTL7	212	196	170	285
PHYHIPL - ANGPTL7	249	19	168	280	PPP1R36 - ANGPTL7	238	4	162	283
CACNB2 - ANGPTL7	207	127	211	186	SPINT1 - ANGPTL7	161	198	242	178
SCN3B - ANGPTL7	282	215	33	307	ANPEP - ANGPTL7	251	240	190	195
SGSM1 - ANGPTL7	247	187	149	198	HRASLS5 - ANGPTL7	170	269	161	48
PHYHIPL - ANGPTL7	249	19	168	280	NSG1 - ANGPTL7	163	184	65	248
ANO5 - ANGPTL7	157	156	38	230	CFAP46 - ANGPTL7	290	122	213	177
ISG20 - ANGPTL7	37	218	218	200	MBOAT1 - ANGPTL7	107	205	289	261
SPTLC3 - ANGPTL7	38	236	249	158	CSDC2 - ANGPTL7	236	164	301	73
RCAN2 - ANGPTL7	27	206	220	153	RSPH9 - ANGPTL7	285	46	209	306
CES4A - ANGPTL7	149	268	275	267	PIFO - ANGPTL7	90	217	257	228
SLCO2A1 - ANGPTL7	136	276	287	264	SLC35G1 - ANGPTL7	51	289	247	155
FAM91A1 - ANGPTL7	121	263	200	203	KCNA2 - ANGPTL7	104	290	273	301
LRRN4CL - ANGPTL7	109	152	260	237	GPR4 - ANGPTL7	91	185	226	222
RPRM - ANGPTL7	266	225	296	29	TMEM125 - ANGPTL7	287	42	286	219
WSCD1 - ANGPTL7	205	258	241	189	SYNM - ANGPTL7	198	244	248	223
CAPN12 - ANGPTL7	103	261	195	213	RIPK4 - ANGPTL7	300	207	292	79
CCSER1 - ANGPTL7	235	222	284	260	SDR42E1 - ANGPTL7	210	179	298	66
MAFF - ANGPTL7	188	239	282	276	RBM11 - ANGPTL7	1	232	276	302
KCNIP4 - ANGPTL7	301	255	304	2	NF2 - ANGPTL7	62	150	277	292
BCR - ANGPTL7	174	190	177	232	NCR3LG1 - ANGPTL7	72	301	204	206
FAM78B - ANGPTL7	87	200	252	212	FAT4 - ANGPTL7	241	201	280	245
SLC6A9 - ANGPTL7	63	259	262	257	ENPP1 - ANGPTL7	222	250	261	272
AFDN-DT - ANGPTL7	47	284	231	169	SH3BGRL2 - ANGPTL7	35	280	194	258
ANKRD35 - ANGPTL7	19	271	272	229	SREBF2 - ANGPTL7	154	249	244	197
COL15A1 - ANGPTL7	81	237	164	150	C9orf129 - ANGPTL7	89	213	264	210

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between ANGPTL7 VS Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

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UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t ANGPTL7	
ANOS1 / ME1 / MOCOS / SMOX / EBF4 / EZR ...	
BAMBI / JOSD1 / PAPLN / EEF1A2 / WFDC2 ...	
GRIK5 / NAMPT / RAPGEFL1 / SCNN1A / MAN1A1 ...	
FANCE / PHACTR1 / ACADL / SSX2IP / ECE1 ...	
SLC16A7 / ABCC4 / TUBA4A / LIF / FLNC ...	
FGF13 / LDLR / ASS1 / LARGE1 / UNC79 ...	
TTC9 / PRRG4 / GIPC2 / RASGEF1B / CDKL2 ...	
KIF21A / RNF157 / SLC47A1 / SLC44A3 ...	
PRSS35 / ASTN2 / CCDC81 / ITIH2 / CACNA2D1 ...	
NCAM2 / SLC26A2 / CLIC2 / GRIP1 / SH3RF2 ...	
ACE / SPON2 / CHRNB2 / CYP3A4 / ARHGEF3 ...	
SLC9B2 / ADCY1 / TRPV6 / PHYHIPL / PPP1R36 ...	
CACNB2 / SPINT1 / SCN3B / ANPEP / SGSM1 ...	
PLAAT5 / PHYHIPL / NSG1 / ANO5 / CFAP46 ...	
ISG20 / MBOAT1 / SPTLC3 / CSDC2 / RCAN2 ...	
RSPH9 / CES4A / PIFO / SLCO2A1 / SLC35G1 ...	
FAM91A1 / KCNA2 / LRRN4CL / GPR4 / RPRM ...	
TMEM125 / WSCD1 / SYNM / CAPN12 / RIPK4 ...	
CCSER1 / SDR42E1 / MAFF / RBM11 / KCNIP4 ...	
NF2 / BCR / NCR3LG1 / FAM78B / FAT4 / SLC6A9 ...	
ENPP1 / AFDN-DT / SH3BGRL2 / ANKRD35 / SREBF2 ...	
COL15A1 / C9orf129	ANGPTL7

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between ANGPTL7 and Individual members.

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